

Towards understanding the quality of OpenStreetMap contributions: Results of an intrinsic quality assessment of OpenStreetMap for Mozambique

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OpenStreetMap (OSM) has made it possible for any volunteer to contribute geographic information, regardless of their level of experience or skills. Since the task of creating geographic information is no longer exclusively performed by trained professionals, data quality can be a concern and has been cited as a hindrance to its use [1]. OSM data quality has often been assessed extrinsically by comparing it to other reference datasets. However, such reference data is not always available and some feature definitions (e.g. wetlands) are subjective. Therefore, intrinsic assessment methods, where the data itself is analysed, have been employed. For example, analysing contributors and their contributions can answer questions, such as: What kind of contributors (e.g. experienced vs newcomers) have worked on the data in the area? In which areas should the data be validated or updated (e.g. where data has been contributed by newer contributors or older non-recurring contributors). As the number of OSM contributors continues to grow, knowledge about their characteristics and the kind of data they contribute is increasing in importance.

In this study, contributors and their contributions to OSM in Mozambique, a country in Southern Africa, were analysed. We chose Mozambique because it received a significant amount of attention in the OSM community following the floods and damages as a result of cyclones Idai and Kenneth in 2019. OSM contributors were characterised in three steps: 1) OSM history data was downloaded, containing information about contributors and their contributions; 2) using k-means cluster analysis and the elbow method for determining an optimal number of clusters, OSM contributors were classified according to the contribution timespan, intensity of editing activities and the type of editing done; 3) based on the classification, contributors were characterised to gain insight into the quality of the data.

OSM history data provides a record of all the edits (or changes) performed on OSM features. Each edit results in an increment in a feature's version number. Each version of a feature is associated with a contributor (called 'user'). The results of the cluster analysis revealed four distinct classes of contributors: most active (n=2552); older non-returning (2676); least productive (n=1301); and recent, perhaps attracted by the disasters (n=3708).

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The most active class of contributors represented 25% of all contributors in the area, with on average the highest numbers of changesets, total contributions, node contributions, way contributions and ways and nodes for which they were the last user to modify them. These volunteers are 'older' contributors who have sustained their contributions in the Mozambique area over a long period of time, with first contributions dating back around 15 years. Compared to other contributors, they have mapped on more days than the others and the average number of edits per feature is higher. Nevertheless, 99.6% of buildings and 84% of ways in the data had been edited twice at most, and most of the buildings appeared in the areas for which mapathons were conducted, outside larger cities. In other parts of the world, editing is more frequent in densely populated areas of cities. More studies in different parts of Africa would contribute to understanding whether the Mozambican pattern is unique or also found in other parts of the African continent.

Similar to the results of other OSM contribution analyses [2], most of the data generated in Mozambique was contributed by a small group of active contributors who have dedicated a significant amount of time to this. Studies have suggested that such contributors are more likely to be experienced and knowledgeable about the project [3, 4] and are therefore more likely to produce data that is of good quality [3, 4]. In this study, individual contributions were clustered, it would be interesting to cluster changesets to assess whether contributor behaviour is consistent across different changesets. Visualizing OSM data based on its history could also provide a quick quality assessment [5].

Even though no absolute statements can be made about the quality of the OSM data for Mozambique, analysing contributors and their contributions provides valuable insight into the quality of the data and can inform efforts to further improve the quality. The results of this study show how one can gain a better understanding of the community that contributes data in a specific area by inspecting history data. Such intrinsic methods should not replace ground truthing or extrinsic methods, but rather complement them by providing alternative ways to gain insight about data quality.

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